

D4.4. Prototypes of wearable strap and sock with sensors (2 prototypes)

J. Cesana [ComfTech], S. Annunziata [ComfTech], L.A. Moltani [ComfTech]

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ThrombUS+ Consortium

ATHENA	Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies, Greece	Eleni Kaldoudi kaldoudi@athenarc.gr
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology Lithuania	Vaidotas Marozas vaidotas.marozas@ktu.lt
VERMON	Vermont SA France	Mathieu Legros m.legros@vermon.com
FRAUNHOFER	Institute for Photonic Microsystems, Fraunhofer Germany	Nicolas Lange Nicolas.Lange@ipms.fraunhofer.de
TELEMED	Telemed Ultrasound Medical Systems Lithuania	Dmitry Novikov d.novikov@pcultrasound.com
EchoNous	EchoNous Inc USA	Pavlos Moustakidis pavlos.moustakidis@echonous.com
MEDIS	medis Medizinische Messtechnik GmbH Germany	Susann Balling sb@medis.company
ComfTech	ComfTech SLR Italy	Lara Alessia Moltani alessia.moltani@comfttech.com
TAU	Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology Tampere University, Finland	Antti Vehkaoja antti.vehkaoja@tuni.fi
LMSU	Lithuanian University of Health Science Lithuania	Andrius Macas andrius.macas@ismu.lt
GNP	Papageorgiou General Hospital Greece	Maria Bigaki pmo@papageorgiou-hospital.gr
CSS-IRCCS	Home Relief of Suffering Hospital Italy	Elvira Grandone e.grandone@operapadrepio.it
HSV	Simon Veil Hospital France	Maxime Gautier maxime.gautier@ch-simoneveil.fr
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies, Germany	Thorsten Prinz thorsten.prinz@vde.com
MEDEA	MEDEA SRL Italy	Pietro Dionisio p.dionisio@medeaproject.eu
PHAZE	Clinical Research and Pharma Consulting SA Greece	Spiros Anagnostopoulos spiros.anagnostopoulos@phazeclinical.com
PBY	PredictBy Research and Consulting SL Spain	Frans Folkvord ffolkvord@predictby.com
SciGen	SciGen Technologies SA Greece	Katerina Pavlidi katerina.Pavlidi@scigentech.com

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Responsible Partner:	ComfTech
Authors:	J. Cesana [ComfTech], S. Annunziata [ComfTech], L.A. Moltani [ComfTech]
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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D4.4 Description

Deliverable 4.4 is the report on the design and development of the wearable prototypes of the ThrombUS+ system. The prototypes consist of two copies of the wearable modules composing the Wearable Ultrasound Device and the Wearable Sensors Network. The report and the prototypes are the results of Task 4.4 *Wearable development and integration with sensors*, where individual sensors, outcomes of T4.1, T4.2, T4.3 and T3.3, are collected and integrated into a unique wearable solution. This task is led by ComfTech, expert in wearable technology solutions.

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Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
CDUS	Compression Duplex Ultrasonography
CSW	Identifier for ThrombUS+ C-shell type Semirigid Wearable
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EA	Elastane
EAC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electronic Actuator Controller
EC	European Commission
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical Impedance Module
EIP	Electrical Impedance Plethysmography
EL	Elastomer
EU	European Union
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Rheography Module
LRR	Light Reflection Rheography
PA	Polyamide
PES	Polyester
PPG	Photoplethysmography
PU	Polyurethane
RUC(s)	Reference Use Case(s)
TL	Task Leader
USM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Monitoring Module
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
WAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module
WSN	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network
WTC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Thigh Cuff
WTE	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Tetrapolar Electrode
WUSD	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Ultrasound Device
XGM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the activities related to ThrombUS+ *Task 4.4 Wearable development and integration with sensors*. The outputs of this task are two prototypes of ThrombUS+ wearable system.

The wearable prototypes are an essential part of the project, contributing both to functional aspects and acceptability of the system by medical experts and patients.

Starting from the technical requirements of specific modules and the iterative process that was carried out, this document delineates in detail their design and development. Also, different configurations of the ThrombUS+ wearable system are presented for different DVT monitoring and prevention methods.

The prototype described will be tested by KTU during *Task 4.5 Testing, signal quality and performance enhancement*.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of *D4.4 Prototypes of wearable strap and sock with sensors* is to create 2 prototypes of the ThrombUS+ wearable system. This document traces the design and development of the first complete prototypes of the system, highlighting the steps followed in collaboration with other partners. These wearable prototypes allow to combine different sensors on the patient and will be first tested by KTU during *T4.5. Testing, signal quality and performance enhancement*.

1.2. Context and structure of the deliverable

Deliverable D4.4. is the outcome of the work conducted within Task *T4.4. Wearable development and integration with sensors*. This Task aims to bring together outcomes of T4.1, T.4.2, T4.3 and T3.3 to create a preliminary prototype of the ThrombUS+ wearable system, combining the individual Modules developed by other Partners.

The following sections present the process that led to the definition of the ThrombUS+ wearable system starting from the development of the individual Modules of the system and then their combination to create different configurations of the system according to the different DVT monitoring and prevention methods.

The result reported in this document should be considered as the starting point for the ThrombUS+ wearable system design. Further iterations can be considered in the upcoming months starting from test results of *T4.5. Testing, signal quality and performance enhancement*, *T6.3. Hardware integration and testing* and further improvement of ultrasound module during the remain months of *WP3 – Wearable ultrasound device*.

2. Development of the Modules

Starting from the modular subdivision of the ThrombUS+ system introduced in the deliverable D2.3¹, the deliverable D2.4² defined the system submodules and divide them into two wearables that can also be worn individually:

- The Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD) includes the C-shell Semirigid Wearable (CSW), the Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC), and the ultrasound Transducer.
- the Wearable Sensors Network (WSN) includes the Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC), the Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC), the Wearable Tetrapolar Electrodes (WTE) and Electrical Impedance Module (EIM) controller, the Light Rheography Module (LRM) sensor, and the Limb Activity Module (LAM) sensors and controller.

Each wearable submodule has been developed individually working with the responsible partner, keeping in mind the forthcoming integration for the first system prototypes and the final prototypes to be delivered in D.4.6.

¹ Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Prinz T, Lukoševičius A, Jurkonis R, Eitminavičius R, Didaskalou S, Vehkaoja A, Ahola R, Slabov A, Jegelevičius D, Balling S, Moutafidou A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A. Technical and functional requirements, Deliverable 2.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897671>

² Cesana J, Annunziata S, Moltani LA, Didaskalou S, Jurkonis R, Marozas V, Lukoševičius A, Schubert F, Balling S, Architectural design of the strap and sock wearable, Deliverable 2.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 December 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352778>

2.1. Two design approaches

Two approaches were followed for the design of the prototypes:

1. Design a garment: sensors are integrated into clothes-like solutions (e.g. shorts, socks, etc.).
2. Design a wearable: sensors are integrated into textile solutions that can be worn (e.g. straps).

Both approaches present peculiar advantages and disadvantages and can be more suitable for specific Reference Use Cases (RUCs) of the ThrombUS+ system as defined in D2.1³. Even if both solutions can be considered for the project and were developed for this D4.4, for D4.6 *Complete prototypes of wearable strap and sock (10 prototypes)*, due to the restricted number of prototypes, only the wearable design approach will be pursued to maximize the possibility of fitting different patients with the same size.

The table below (Table 1) presents the advantages and disadvantages of the two approaches and indicates the most suitable RUCs for each. RUCs are numbered following D2.1.:

- RUC #1 – Neurosurgery
- RUC #2 – Lower limb orthopaedic surgery
- RUC #3 - Cardiovascular surgery and risk
- RUC #4 – Pregnancy and postpartum
- RUC #5 – Cancer and oncological treatment
- RUC #6 – Obesity
- RUC #7 – Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders

A possible classification of the most suitable RUCs per approach can be based on *usability* and *acceptability* criteria⁴, by assessing for instance the duration of the expected use of the ThrombUS+ system or the potential level of movement and comfort of the user while wearing it. For example, patients undergoing surgery (RUCs #1, #2, #3) are likely to use the system mainly while lying in bed, thus having a lower level of movement. Patients in these contexts are usually assisted by medical staff, who can help to counteract the increased sensitivity to positioning and movement. On the other hand, patients with a higher degree of mobility, such as those who are pregnant, undergoing cancer treatment, affected by overweight or obesity, or living with an autoimmune disease (RUCs #4, #5, #6, #7) may use the system to perform prevention exercises while standing or even moving. Logically, these patients would benefit from a design that is more intuitive, easy to use, and allows for greater autonomy. Also, the period of use foreseen for RUCs #1, #2, #3 is short-term (days), while it is expected to be of long-term (months, years, rest of life) for RUCs #4, #5, #6, #7.

Table 1. Advantages, disadvantages and most suitable RUCs for the two design approaches.

	Garment	Wearable
Advantages	Does not require the positioning of the sensors, once the garment is worn everything is already in place	Provides more adjustability to different sizes

³ Segal LJ, Puppo F, Folkvord F, Patient-centric cases and requirements definition, Deliverable 2.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 28 June 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12554621>

⁴ Following the definitions provided in D2.1, *usability* is understood as defined in ISO 9241-11:2018(en) Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts as “the extent to which a system, product or service can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use”. *Acceptability*, for its part, is understood as that property of an adaptive system of interacting components that both influences and is influenced by user engagement, and is affected by factors such as safety, comfort and ease of use.

	Wearing procedure is more intuitive	Can be one-size
	Is more suitable for long-term use	Is more suitable for short-term use
Disadvantages	Requires several sizes to get the right fit and positioning	Each part has to be positioned so it requires more instructions and time for those who have to have it worn or wear it
	Can require specific openings to facilitate wearing procedure	Can be more sensitive to patient movement
Most suitable RUCs	#4, #5, #6, #7	#1, #2, #3

Due to the characteristics of the C-shell Semirigid Wearable (CSW) and the Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC), they will follow only the wearable approach, while for the Electrical Impedance Module (EIM), the Light Rheography Module (LRM) and the Limb activity Module (LAM) it is possible to consider both garment and wearable approaches, creating respectively a sock and shorts solution and a semi-independent straps solution.

The iterative process described in the following sections for the individual modules led to the creation of the first complete prototypes of ThrombUS+ wearable system, including:

- The Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD) prototype, composed of the C-shell Semirigid Wearable (CSW) and the Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC).
- The Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) prototype.
- The Wearable Sensors Network (WSN) garment-approach prototype, composed of shorts and sock.
- The Wearable Sensors Network (WSN) wearable-approach prototype, composed of semi-independent straps for thigh, calf and foot.

To fulfil the purpose of this deliverable (the creation of 2 prototypes of the ThrombUS+ wearable system), two units of each of the aforementioned modules have been produced.

2.2. Electrical Impedance Module

Wearable parts related to Electrical Impedance Module (EIM) have been developed in collaboration with TAU, Task Leader for T4.1. *Advancements in impedance plethysmography and spectroscopy sensors and hardware*. Additional information about the impedance plethysmography sensors and other submodules of EIM can be found in D4.1. *Sensors and Processing Software for Electrical Impedance Plethysmography DVT Detection*⁵.

Technical requirements defined for EIM and related to WTE are listed below:

- TR_EIM_01: Electrode Configuration: A tetrapolar electrode configuration, where the two outer electrodes are used for current injection, and the two inner electrodes for voltage measurement, must be used. This configuration is preferred over the bipolar configuration as it minimizes confounding factors, particularly the effects of skin electrode impedance.
- TR_EIM_02: Washable electroconductive textiles must be used for all electrodes.

⁵ Verho J, Ahola R, Maja S, Vehkaoja A. Sensors and processing software for electrical impedance plethysmography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540486>

2.2.1. Prototypes iteration

The initial prototypes of EIM-related wearable were made to evaluate different types, configurations and performances of textile electrodes, starting from initial requirements:

- Textile electrodes placed on at least 4 points of the lower limb, covering the entire circumference.
- Contact with the skin, ensuring good adherence.

Each iteration of the EIM-related wearable prototypes has been tested by TAU in combination with their EIM controller and EIM software.

The first iteration included different proposals of textile electrodes:

- Type 1 is an adjustable strap with Velcro, internally covered with conductive fabric.
- Type 2 is an adjustable strap with Velcro, internally covered with independent textile electrodes.
- Type 3 is loose textile electrode.

According to TAU feedback, the second iteration of EIM-related wearable prototypes only included Type 1. In fact, a continuous stripe of conductive fabric demonstrated better results for the required application. These second prototypes included 4 adjustable straps covered with conductive fabric to be placed on the calves, and 2 adjustable straps covered with conductive fabric to be placed on the thighs.

For the third iteration of EIM-related wearable prototypes TAU suggested to replace Velcro adjustment with spring stoppers. This solution enhances adherence on the skin and allows easier and faster adaptation to different circumferences, also considering their following integration into the WSN. Also, for the 3rd version, 4 smaller adjustable bands for calves and 2 bigger adjustable bands for thighs were produced.

The first integration of the Wearable Tetrapolar Electrodes submodule (WTE) into the WSN has been done considering the previous iterations of single bands and dimensions suggested by TAU. Four stripes of textile electrodes have been integrated into the first prototype of the sock locating them on the calf. Each of the electrodes has its own textile wire to which the EIM controller can be connected and its own spring stopper adjusted for skin contact.

A second integration into calf sleeve has been done for TAU to validate the position of the electrodes. This second sock has a full-length zip and two spring stoppers for each electrode stripes. Having two of them should ensure uniformity when pulled. Also, in this version, the wires are collected in the same area of the prototypes, to facilitate the connection and reduce the points where the wearable is connected to wires.

A third integration into calf sleeve of the WTE has been done for the final WSN prototype. In this version, following clinics suggestions, the zip is replaced with Velcro.

For the second design approach, two semi-independent straps with textile electrodes have been developed. The two straps, both integrating two electrodes' stripes, are linked by a vertical textile loop. This solution gives more freedom to adjust the straps on the patient using the respective Velcro and guide the healthcare personnel during the wearing procedure keeping the distance between the straps fixed. The loop is also designed to be a guide for the positioning of a third strap that includes LRM sensor and LAM sensor.

The textile electrodes integrated here are made with a different conductive textile, already tested for biocompatibility, in order to compare the two conductive textiles performances and durability.

Due to the current dimensions of the EIM controller, for these prototypes is expected to have it placed beside the patient's bed and not wearing it on the leg. Another solution can consider an additional accessory as waist bag or pouch to carry the EIM controller if movement is required. The EIM controller is attached to WTE through alligator clips.

The proposed solutions meet the defined technical requirements. Both respects the required tetrapolar electrode configuration and include washable textile electrodes.

2.3. Light Rheography Module

The wearable parts related to Light Rheography Module (LRM) has been developed in collaboration with MEDIS, Task Leader for T4.2. *Advancements in light reflection rheography and hardware*. Additional information about Light Reflection Rheography Sensor and other submodules of LRM can be found in D4.2. *Sensors and Processing Software for Light Reflection Rheography DVT Detection*⁶.

Technical requirement defined for LRM and related to the wearable part is listed below:

- TR_LRM_08: Attachment: LRM modules must be attachable to lower extremity segments using comfortable Velcro straps.

2.3.1. Prototypes iteration

LRM-related wearable part should consider:

- Light Reflection Rheography (LRR) sensor doesn't require direct skin contact, but fabric must ensure no interferences with the LRR sensor activity.
- Easy positioning and removing of the LRR sensor.
- Good location on the limb, about 10cm above the ankle.

As a first step, 7 textile samples (Figure 1) have been selected and shared with MEDIS to evaluate suitable materials to work with the LRR sensor. MEDIS performed the same test on all the different samples.

Figure 1. Textile samples tested by MEDIS

After comparing the LRR measurements obtained with the sensor placed directly on the skin and the measurements obtained by attaching the textile samples between the skin and the sensor, samples 1 and 2 were found to be the most suitable for the wearable design.

The first integration of LRM-related parts of the wearable into the has been done considering MEDIS conclusions and assuming that the final dimensions of the sensor will be 45mm diameter and 15mm height.

Between the two samples of textile, sample 1 is preferred due to a lower increment of required LED current (approx. 220% for sample 1, approx. 300% for sample 2). Both textiles are OEKO-TEX STANDARD 100 class II certified, meaning that they passed safety tests for the presence of harmful substances and is intended to be used in direct contact with the skin. Characteristics of these meshed textiles do not permit to use them for the whole wearable prototypes, so the LRM sensor will require a pocket made of the selected textile

⁶ Balling S, Querengässer J, Schubert F, Sensors and processing software for light reflection rheography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540537>

integrated into the wearable. The same solution is followed for the final prototype of WSN following the garment approach.

Another solution follows the second design approach. In this case, the LRM sensor is placed inside a separated pocket that can slide along an adjustable strap.

This solution gives more freedom to place the LRM sensor according to the single patient, and the Velcro adjustment ensures good adherence to the skin. Due to the required position on the calf of LRM sensor and LAM sensor, this strap includes both of them and will be placed in between the two EIM straps described in the previous Subsection 2.2.

To guide the wearing procedure, this strap is made to pass inside the textile loop that joins the EIM straps, creating a three semi-independent straps wearable solution.

The second solution (wearable approach) meets the defined technical requirement of having Velcro strap to attach the LRM sensor on the lower limb. The first solution (garment approach) also includes Velcro and, even if it cannot be defined as a strap, it achieves the same objective of quick wearing procedure and comfort.

2.4. Limb Activity Module

Wearable parts related to Limb Activity Module (LAM) has been developed in collaboration with KTU, Task Leader for T4.3 *Lower limb activity sensor network*. Additional information about Limb Activity Sensors can be found in D4.3. *Sensors and Processing Software for Lower Limb Activity Pattern Recognition*⁷.

Technical requirements defined for LAM and related to the wearable part are listed below:

- TR_LAM_03: The Number of IMU Sensors: The minimum quantity is three—one for each leg segment (foot, calf, and thigh).
- TR_LAM_08: Attachment: LAM modules must be attachable to lower extremity segments using comfortable Velcro straps.

2.4.1. Prototypes iteration

LAM-related wearable part should consider:

- 1 IMU sensor for each leg segment (foot, calf, and thigh).
- Good stability during movement of the patient.
- Optional skin contact to include also PPG sensor.
- Presence of wire to connect each sensor.

As a first iteration, two solutions were evaluated to integrate LAM sensors into the wearable: using snaps and using custom made thermoformed pockets. Even if the first solution ensures quick fastening of the sensors, the main problems are the lack of stability and the lack of skin contact. The second solution can ensure stability and skin contact but, due to the presence of the wire, it can be inconvenient and can take much longer to place them.

The second iteration took KTU's request for skin contact into greater consideration, keeping in mind quick positioning and good stability. This iteration includes a semirigid LAM sensor housing, to be integrated into the wearable, where the LAM sensor can be attached sliding it along the guide rail.

For the third iteration, the goal was to avoid additional semirigid parts into the wearable, so the housing proposed in the second iteration is removed and replaced with a fabric alternative. Starting from KTU proposal,

⁷ Jucevičius M, Marozas V, Daukantas S, Lukoševičius A. Sensors and processing software for lower limb activity pattern recognition (2 sets), Deliverable 4.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540539>

the third iteration includes an elastic band with a rectangular cut which works as housing for the LAM sensor. This elastic band is placed above a hole in the wearable, ensuring skin contact for the sensor once it is in position.

This housing solution has been integrated into sock and shorts prototypes following the first design approach. On the garments, three housing points are arranged: thigh, calf and foot.

Both sock and shorts are designed for facilitated wearing procedure thanks to a full-length lateral opening that avoids wearing them from the foot.

These prototypes were shared with KTU and LSMU for further considerations about technical requirements and acceptability for clinicians and patients. These considerations can be found in Section 3.

For the second iteration of the shorts and sock, the full-length zips are replaced with Velcro but the housing solution for the LAM remained the same.

Following the wearable design approach, LAM sensors can be also located on 3 independent straps with Velcro for thigh, calf and foot. The calf strap was already mentioned in the previous subsection, since it also includes the LRM sensor. Instead, the thigh and foot straps include only the LAM sensor. All three of them allow a quick and easy adjustment on the patient using Velcro.

A ribbon cable will connect the LAM sensors to the LAM controller. The LAM controller will be placed on the waist using an additional waist accessory, described in section 2.6.

Both proposed solutions (garment and wearable) meet the requirement of having three IMU sensors on the leg. The second solution (wearable approach) meet the requirement of having Velcro strap to attach the LAM sensors on the lower limb. The first solution (garment approach) also includes Velcro and, even if it cannot be defined as a strap, it achieves the same objective of quick wearing procedure and comfort.

2.5. C-shell semirigid wearable

C-shell type Semirigid Wearable (CSW) is a submodule of the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM), used in combination with Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC), to perform Compression Duplex Ultrasonography (CDUS). Additional information about CSW can be found in D3.3. *Precise, silent tissue compression actuator prototypes*⁸.

Technical requirements for CSW are listed below:

- TR_WAM_01: 01 Structure: The WAM must include (a) a C-shell type semirigid wearable textile for the integration of a detachable ultrasound transducer and air bladders, and (b) an electronic actuator controller. The shell and textile must be robust and skin compatible to ensure durability and prevent irritation during prolonged use.
- TR_WAM_10: Durability and Lifetime: The actuator is a reusable device and must withstand several thousand cycles of operation. Materials used in the actuator that come into direct or indirect contact with the body must meet biocompatibility standards (e.g., ISO 10993) to avoid adverse reactions. The device should withstand multiple sterilization cycles without compromising functionality or material integrity.
- TR_WAM_13: Reusability: WAM must be reusable, enabling washing and disinfection of its parts.

⁸ R. Eitminavičius, R. Jurkonis, V. Marozas, S. Daukantas, A. Sakalauskas, A. Slabov, Precise Tissue Compression Actuator, Deliverable D3.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 04 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540479>

2.5.1. Prototypes iteration

The C-shell type Semirigid Wearable is used to apply compression on patient's thigh to close the veins, its characteristics are:

- It is composed of two rigid frames, one frame with locking slot for transducer and one frame to support the bladders.
- Its main location is on the upper part of the thigh.
- It can be adjusted to different thigh circumferences.

The iterations of the CSW are based on the 3D printed rigid frames, designed by KTU. Two softer 3D printed parts are also added to the frame to reduce possible discomfort.

Starting from the 3D printed mock-up, different iterations of the textile envelop for the rigid plastic frames were evaluated and tested by KTU.

For the first iteration, the same method of KTU was followed, using the lateral slots of the frames to pass the adjustment straps through. Velcro is also added to improve the fastening, but this method can present poor usability. Also, the bladders are integrated into the textile envelop that covers the frame.

For the second iteration a new adjustment and fastening method has been conceived: two lateral pieces covered with Velcro loop are added to the plain frame envelop. These parts can improve usability and reduce steps to wear the CSW. Also, following KTU suggestion, the bladders are now separate from the frames and are placed inside a separate pocket. This means that they can be slightly moved to improve their position independently from the frames.

For the third iteration, the lateral Velcro parts of the plain frames are modified to give more stability. Also, some textile parts are now more rigid to ensure that the pressure of the bladders is kept inside the frames, e.g. the blue part of the bladders pocket.

Also, for this iteration the pocket for the bladders has a double layer of textile aiming to create two different spaces, one for a bigger bladder and one for two smaller bladders. This solution ensures the possibility to use different bladders with this component.

The bladders of the CSW will be connected to the EAC with tubes for the air flow. The EAC is a hardware component designed to be mounted on the thigh. Its shape follows the curve of the rigid frame, allowing its positioning above the CSW.

Proposed solution meets the defined technical requirements of structure and reusability. Biocompatibility and resistance to multiple sterilization cycles will be tested.

2.6. Wearable Thigh Cuff

Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) is a submodule of the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM), used in combination with Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC) and Electrical Impedance Module (EIM) to perform Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP). Additional information about CSW can be found in D3.3. *Precise, silent tissue compression actuator prototypes*⁸.

2.6.1. Prototypes iteration

The Wearable Thigh Cuff is used to compress patient's thigh to close the veins, its characteristics are:

- It is located on the lower part of the thigh.
- It is long enough to cover the whole circumference of this area.
- It includes 1 bladder.

The first iteration of the WTC took into consideration a bigger dimension of the bladder, previously supposed (320x165mm). This first prototype presents an internal pocket for the bladder and a Velcro adjustment

solution. It has also an additional waist adjustment that can improve stability of the wearable in some specific cases. The external material (Neoprene coupled with Polyamide) of this prototype allows to the hook parts of the Velcro to attach everywhere on it, ensuring maximum adaptability to different thigh circumferences.

For the second iteration, the additional waist adjustment is separated from the cuff, permitting it to be removed if not needed, i.e. if the patient is lying in bed. The connecting piece between the waist band and the cuff also guarantee adaptability to different thigh lengths. These addition parts can also be used with WSN to mount the LAM controller and add more stability to the LAM sensor strap for thigh.

Internal part of this second iteration is also covered with rigid Polyurethane to stiffen the soft external material, keeping the pressure of the inflated bladder inside.

The need for a wider tube for air passage led to the decision of using bladders provided by MEDIS, instead of other bladders on the market. This bladder is smaller than the one used for the first and the second iteration, therefore the dimensions of the WTC prototype are modified accordingly in the third iteration and the final height is 140 mm, reducing the area covered on the thigh.

Furthermore, this third version follows LMSU partner suggestion to consider that common patient weight is approximately 120 kg, so the length of the cuff is incremented to 100 cm to cover larger thigh circumferences (up to 65 cm). Another feature improved from previous iterations is that the tube of the bladder is moved to the outside.

The bladder of the WTC will be connected to the EAC with tubes for the air flow. The EAC can work both with WTC and CSW , in this case it can be positioned beside the patient's bed or attached on the WTC.

2.7. Materials and care

The table below summarizes the characteristics of the chosen textiles for each of the components described above. All the materials that require skin contact are certified OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I and class II, ensuring that they are safe for the skin and they are already tested for the presence of harmful substances.

Table 2. Materials and related certifications for each component described in Section 2.

Component		Textile composition	Certifications
EIM	WTE	Alternative 1: 56 % PA, 16 % EL, 26.5 % Silver, 1.5 % Nitrile rubber Coating ± 10 %	RoHS, REACH, OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I
		Alternative 2: 59% PA Silver + 41% INOX	ISO 10993
LRM	White pocket	75% PA, 25% EA	OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class II
LAM	Housing	35% EA, 65% PES + Films 100% PU	OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I
CSW	Internal part	76% PA (Recycled), 24% EA (Recycled) + 100% Nylon + Films 100% PU	OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I or class II
	External part	84% Nylon, 16% EA + 100% PA	-
WTC	Internal part	76% PA (Recycled), 24% EA (Recycled) + Films 100% PU	OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I
	External part	Neoprene coupled with PA	-
WSN	Garments	76% PA (Recycled), 24% EA (Recycled)	OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I
	Straps	65% PES, 35% EA + 72% PES, 28% latex + Films made of PU + 84% Nylon, 16% EA + 100% PA	OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I or class II

All the different parts are designed to be washed or sanitised and therefore all electronics and bladders with tubes are removable. Possible solutions for cleaning are:

- Amuchina Spray Disinfettante, a surgical medical device suitable for disinfecting textiles; it can be used before washing cycle.
- Surgical medical devices such as disinfectants and detergents based on sodium hypochlorite, sodium chloride; to be used before or during washing cycle.
- Cold wash and ozone disinfection.

The maximum washing temperature for the prototypes is 60°C, the textile electrodes used for EIM are the most sensitive part of the system, it is important to follow cleaning instructions to avoid any damages. Care instruction will be specified in the instructions for use to guide the users.

3. Configurations of the ThrombUS+ wearable system

Different configurations of ThrombUS+ wearable system, combining the modules described in the previous chapter, are designed to be used in different DVT monitoring and prevention methods defined in the D6.1 *Product Design Specifications*⁹ and listed below:

- Operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography.
- Operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography for DVT monitoring.
- Operator-independent Light Reflection Rheography-Based Monitoring of DVT.
- Operator-independent Serious Gaming for DVT prevention.

In this section, the different configurations are presented following these four methods. Detailed description of each method can be found in D6.1, mentioned above.

3.1. Operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography

Figure 2. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

Operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography scenario involves ThrombUS+ modules highlighted in Figure 2 and requires the patient to wear the CSW on the thigh as shown in Figure 3.

⁹ Marozas V, Portokallidis N, Jurkonis R, Jucevičius M, Eitminavičius R, Lukoševičius A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A, Sonda A, Moutafidou A, Cesana J, Moustakidis P, Lange N, Balling S, Querengässer J, Legros M, Novikov D, Maja S, Prinz T, Kaldoudi E. Product Design Specifications, Deliverable 6.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 28 February 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930624>

Figure 3. ThrombUS+ system configuration for operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography.

3.2. Operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography for DVT monitoring

Figure 4. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

Operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography scenario involves ThrombUS+ modules highlighted in Figure 4 and requires the patient to wear EIM-related wearable and the WTC. Following the two design approaches, the configuration for this method can include WSN sock and WTC or EIM straps and WTC as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. ThrombUS+ system configuration for operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography: garment design approach (a, b), wearable design approach (c).

3.3. Operator-Independent Light Reflection Rheography-Based Monitoring of DVT

Figure 6. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for LRM-based DVT monitoring: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

Operator-independent Light Reflection Rheography scenario involves ThrombUS+ modules highlighted in Figure 6 and requires the patient to wear LRM-related wearable and LAM-related wearable. Following the

two design approaches, the configuration for this method can include WSN sock and shorts or WSN straps, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. ThromBUS+ system configuration for operator-independent LRM-based DVT monitoring: garment design approach (a), wearable design approach (b).

3.4. Operator-independent Serious Gaming for DVT prevention

Figure 8. The ThromBUS+ subsystem for DVT prevention: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

Operator-independent Serious Gaming scenario involves ThromBUS+ modules highlighted in Figure 8 and requires the patient to wear LAM-related wearable and LRM-related wearable. Following the two design

approaches, the configuration for this method can include WSN sock and shorts or WSN straps and is the same of the previous method (Figure 7).

4. Conclusions and next steps

During the development of these prototypes, two preliminary evaluations were made by clinical partners. The first one was conducted during the third Project Meeting in Foggia (Italy). Here clinicians had the possibility to see some initial iterations of prototypes and to share their observations.

Mainly, their attention focused on:

- Fastening solutions: No zip in contact with the skin, Velcro is always preferred.
- Design: Ensure easy wearing procedure.
- Sizes: Clinical Study A will collect patients' measures, these data should be used.
- Materials: Wearables must not create compression on the leg and easy cleaning procedure.

The second evaluation involved only LMSU partner, to whom KTU showed the first prototype of sock and shorts for LAM and the second iteration of WTC prototypes. Their suggestions are summarised below and have already been implemented in the final prototypes of deliverable D4.4:

- Fastening solutions: Doctors are strongly suggesting Velcro and are quite sceptical of zips.
- Design: Alternative solutions for the shorts are recommended, to avoid pull-on parts. Foot part can use Velcro too.
- Sizes: if one size is considered, it should ensure a wide adjustment. From their experience, common patient weight is ~120 kg, most people's height can range at least from 160 to 190 cm tall and their shoe size can range from 38 to 45. These data can be the starting point for the prototypes, before Clinical Study A results.
- Materials: WTC material is a good solution, while they are not confident on shorts and sock textile. Disinfection has to be considered after each use. A
- LAM Sensor's positions: on the shin it should be rotated 45 deg. to exterior side, to be placed on the flat part.

All the final prototypes will be tested and evaluated by KTU during T4.5. Individual modules will be also tested by the partner in charge of the corresponding task. Furthermore, the upcoming fourth Project Meeting will be an occasion to present and receive feedback from all the Consortium.

The next steps:

- Collect results from T 4.5 to fix any arising issues.
- All the materials in contact with patient's skin will be tested following ISO 10993 for evaluating the biocompatibility. The decision to use OEKO-TEXT STANDARD 100 CLASS I and II certified textiles ensures that they are already tested for the presence of hazardous substances, and it should ensure a good result of the tests.
- Evaluate alternative solutions to manage the gel used for the Compression Ultrasonography. An additional component can be designed to cover the frame with transducer slot, avoiding the gel to move around the CSW making cleaning procedure more difficult.

The development of the ThrombUS+ wearable prototypes marked a crucial step in integrating multiple sensor technologies into two functional wearable solutions: the Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD) and the Wearable Sensors Network (WSN). Throughout an iterative and collaborative process, we designed, evaluated, and refined prototypes for each submodule, incorporating valuable feedback from clinical

partners to ensure technical performance, usability, and patient comfort. Preliminary evaluations highlighted important lessons, such as the preference for Velcro fastenings, the necessity of size adaptability, and the prioritization of biocompatible, washable materials.

As a result of this work, two design approaches, garment-based and wearable-based, were followed, offering flexibility to address the diverse needs of different patient groups and use cases. The prototypes developed under Deliverable D4.4 form a solid foundation for further technical and clinical evaluation.